

Nonlocality Imposed by Special Relativity on Quantum Free Particles?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 28, 2022

In a previous note (1) we considered a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ and $t=t_0$ and argued this transforms to E', p' with $x'/t'=v$. Thus a single system may be Lorentz transformed to create particles with m_0 and all velocities. We suggested that all of these particles are on the same footing in a sense. In this note we try to investigate what this "footing" is. In particular, we suggest nonlocality. A particle with rest mass m_0 , likely occupies some region of space, but is treated as a point (i.e. $x=0$) which may be the center of mass. The idea of a particle considered as a point is carried over into special relativity i.e motion. In Newtonian mechanics the particle is also considered to be a point. We argue that even though a particle "system" with m_0 at $x=0$ and $t=t_0$ is a point and that after moving there may still be an $x'/t' = v$ pertaining to one point representing the system, the localization of m_0 at $x=0$ may be transformed into a localization in every constant moving frame. This localization seems to be linked to the idea of x and t being independent in $-Et+px$ just as a particle at $x=0$ and $t=t_0$ at rest treats x and t as independent.

Thus we argue that the localization is the "same footing" of particles with different v and hence momenta mv .

The dot product $-Et+px = A$ is $-m_0c^2$ for the rest frame which tends to 0 for $v \rightarrow 0$. For any frame, $t=b/E$ and $x=b/p$ yields the same $A=0$. Furthermore $x=b/p$ and $t=b/E$ is a recipe which holds in all frames and describes nonlocality or a "trapped" length associated with the moving particle. This trapped length is not associated with time because x and t are independent. In other words the system moves with a speed of $v=x'/t'$, but the particle is "trapped" within a wavelength of the order $1/p$ in the sense that there is a cycling probability as the particle moves through space ignoring time. One does not simply have a point at rest transformed into a point in motion describing all aspects of the moving particle. If one considers $x=0$ and $x=1/p$, particles with different p values may follow the same probability distribution associated with energy flow in the region of one wavelength. If one ignores the motion $v=x'/t'$, then since time is ignored it is as if one has a particle with different probabilities to be at different x points. In a bound quantum state, time is physically dropped and these probabilities are linked to actual densities. For a moving particle (in one direction) one must consider the point motion $v=x'/t'$, but also kind of periodic trapping of the particle in space (not linked to time).

In order to quantify this for a quantum free particle, one may consider the idea of a particle system with a length proportional to $1/p$ which is consistent with $P(x)=\text{constant}$. In particular, one may take the square root of 1 so to speak to obtain $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. This also follows from eigenvalue equations of $A = -Et+px$ i.e. $-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$.

It should be noted (as stated above) that $\exp(ipx)$ does not involve time. Thus the trapping is in space and may occur over a long period of time if the velocity is very slow i.e. $1/p$ is very large. In a sense the particle is trapped in a kind of periodic motion in space. There is locality in the sense of position $x'/t'=v$, but not in the sense of the trapped periodic motion. The nonlocality seems to exist on one opposite scales than the usual point velocity. For example, if a particle has a very small velocity then $x'/t'=v \rightarrow 0$ i.e. one thinks in terms of a very small x' , but $1/p$ is very large.

Special Relativity and the Idea of Nonlocality

Special relativity deals with transformations due to constant moving frames. Classical mechanics associates particles or even systems with a single point, namely the center-of-mass. Thus it seems automatic to consider x', t' as representing a center-of-mass and considering a scenario of points in motion. The Lorentz invariant inner product (which is also the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical action if $v=x/t$) $A = -Et+px$, however, seems to suggest two ways of maintaining A constant. The first is the usual Lorentz transformation applied to the 4-vectors (p, E) and (x, t) , but we argue that there is also the notion of nonlocality i.e. a fixed length in the problem (and independently a fixed time). A particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$ transforms into $E' = m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ and $p = Ev$ with $x'/t' = v$. $A = -m_0 t_0$ in the rest frame. For t approaching 0 this becomes 0, but so does $t' = b/E$ and $x' = b/p$ for any frame. Thus one may have an identical A in all frames provided one introduces nonlocality i.e. breaks with the idea of the system being a point and considers t and x as independent. It may be noted that in the rest frame, $x=0$ and $t=t_0$ are also independent. The particle may still be treated as a point, but it is confined to a region of b/p i.e. a wavelength if one ignores time. At the same time the entire system moves with velocity v . This nonlocality seems to link at m_0, v combinations which follow from $m_0, x=0, t=t_0$. In other words all of these moving particles are created by different Lorentz transformations of the same initial state (similar to a rotated vector). $x'/t' = v$ are different because the different systems move at different velocities, but all systems may be put on the same "scaled" footing by introducing a length proportional to $1/p$. Thus p scales space. One might then speculate that a periodic function would describe such a "trapped" nonlocal system which nevertheless moves through space with a single velocity $v=x'/t'$.

In other words we argue that special relativity may be seen to introduce nonlocality or a length scale for a particle with momentum p . What is considered to be a trapped particle with energy m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$, is a trapped particle with momentum p within a length proportional to $1/p$. Thus $\cos(px)$ from $\exp(ipx)$ a free particle wavelength does not show the direction of motion, but does show the trapping length of the particle which still remains a point. It should be noted that the idea of a particle being trapped in a length $1/p$ with different probabilities at different x points means that one ignores time in the problem. There has to be a physical reason to do this. For example, in a bound state one has a stationary density and may drop time. In a two-slit interaction, one may drop time from the interaction with the two slit A fast moving particle and a slow one produce the same interference pattern if $m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$.

Finding the Free Particle Probability

If special relativity imposes a scaled length which creates a scaled equality among different m_0, v particles, one may ask how one may represent the probability within such a region. A possible consideration (mentioned in previous notes) is to first consider the classical idea of $P(x)=\text{constant}$. The square root of this in a sense (which takes into account px) is $\exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. This is a periodic function which allows for the nonlocal region to be repeated, but suggests that "shifts" in position which are a fraction of the wavelength (and not a multiple) lead to nonaligned localization regions i.e. interference. As discussed in other notes, $\exp(ipx)$ also follows as an eigenvalue equation using $-id/dx$ partial $\exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ where $A = -Et+px$.

What is interesting is that $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$. $\cos(px)$ does not show the direction in which the particle moves. In other words $\cos(px)$ should show the trapping (described by a systematic probability) of both a forward and backward moving particle. $\cos(px)$ itself may be written as $.5 (\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx))$ suggesting backwards and forwards trapped motion in a local region of length proportional to $1/p$. Thus even quantum free motion seems to be quite complicated when compared with moving points. A kind of trapped wavelike motion exists within $1/p$ lengths and one requires a shifted distribution $\sin(px)$ to create a system which moves either to the right or left.

P→0 and Large Wavelengths

A system with m_0 at $x=0$, $t=t_0$ is trapped at a point i.e. $x=0$. If momentum becomes very small, for example due to low velocity, this scenario should approach m_0 , $x=0$, but it doesn't. Instead there is a large wavelength proportional to $1/p$. What approximates the rest scenario is the point Lorentz transformation i.e. $x' = v/\sqrt{1-vv}$ and $t' = t_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$. For a tiny v , x' approaches $v t_0$ or 0 and t' approaches t_0 . Thus x', t' suggest the system is very close to $x=0, t=t_0$, but the nonlocality picture suggests the particle may be anywhere within a very large wavelength. How are these ideas compatible? For example, a quantum particle with a tiny velocity (and also tiny p) may be moving through space toward a two-slit apparatus. The speed through space should be compatible with $v \rightarrow 0$, but the physical spacing of the slits is compatible with $1/p$ which is large. In order to resolve this issue, one may note that $x'/t' = v$ makes use of time while $\exp(ipx)$ does not. Thus we argue that there is a kind of cycling which only depends on space. The particle is trapped in a large region of space, but not at any particular time, (although a rough time exists for a particle reaching the two slit apparatus) but through $\exp(ipx)$ which governs its probability distribution. In most quantum problems a particle moves at incredibly fast speeds e.g. 10 to the power of 7 m/s and wavelengths are on the order of the length of the system or smaller.

If one considers time, then for a very small velocity: $E = m_0 + .5 m_0 v^2$ and $\exp(-i(m_0 t)) \exp(-i .5 m_0 v^2 t)$ shows that the second factor linked to velocity changes very slowly in time. Thus the trapping for low v is very weak. It takes a long time and a long distance for it to be manifested.

For high momenta (speeds) one thinks of a large x' in $x'/t' = v$, but $1/p$ is very small. Thus one sees again the opposite effect in length associated with the movement of a point and the cycling-trapping effect.

Conclusion

In conclusion we suggest that even though classical mechanics and traditional views of special relativity treat a particle as a point, it may be that special relativity dictates that moving particles be trapped within $1/p$ regions with time being dropped (except for a rough time corresponding to system motion in a one directional scenario. For bound states, one may drop time altogether for $V(x)$. One may "create" moving particles from a rest particle with mass m_0 at $x=0$ and $t=t_0$. This particle is localized albeit at a point. A Lorentz transformation leads to E', p'

and $x'/t'=v$ which still suggests a moving point. The Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ is also compatible with a single point, but has a second solution linked to nonlocality i.e. a specific length proportional to $1/p$ and a time proportional to $1/E$. This leads to $A=0$ which is the same as $-m_0$ to as to $\rightarrow 0$. In other words we suggest that nonlocality i.e. trapping of a particle within a length $1/p$ with a scaled probability distribution keeps all m_0, v particles the same one a scaled trapped footing. I.e. p scales x , but otherwise the particles undergo the same probability distribution from $x=0$ to $x=1/p$. In other words a system with a specific length is created, but this system moves through space at $v=x'/t'$. Within the length $1/p$ one does not consider time. In such a case x' is like the center of mass of the system so to speak. As a result of this physical trapping, one may have phase shifts i.e. length shifts which are nonintegers multiplied by $1/p$.

A solution which describes this type of system is $\exp(ipx)$. This may be thought of as the "square root" of $P(x)=\text{constant}$ or as a solution of an eigenvalue equation $-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. It may also be noted that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ means that one has the same phase in all frames.

As a result, we suggest that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ may have two sets of implications. One is linked to the changing of a point (e.g. m_0 at $x=0, t=t_0$) to $x'/t'=v$ and E', p' as well as the creation of a region of space proportional to $1/p$ in which a particle is trapped. The whole system moves with $v=x'/t'$, but two shifted probability distributions are needed to describe it namely $\exp(ipx)$. In the rest frame, the particle is also trapped, but at a point $x=0$. The trapping in the region of $1/p$, however, is not linked to time and so a small velocity i.e. small p may lead to a very large wavelength which would be realized over a large time as the nonlocality is associated with $v=x'/t'$ motion. One may note that for a free quantum particle i.e. an electron which does not interact, one considers motion through space of $v=x'/t'$, but assigns a phase of px to each x point. One does not think of the electron as being somewhere within the wavelength proportional to $1/p$. If the electron, however, reaches a two slit apparatus, then it can sense both slits if they are a wavelength or so apart so the idea of the electron being within the $1/p$ region seems to hold as it does in the case of a bound quantum object.

References

1. Rugeri, Francesco R. Special Relativity, Lagrangian Theory and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2022)